

On the Implementation of Temporal Fusion Transformers for Target Recognition and Tracking

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Abstract—Time series forecasting is advancing across many domains, offering promising performance. However, efforts to apply forecasting techniques to direction of arrival estimation and array signal processing are limited. This paper explores the implementation of temporal fusion transformers (TFTs) for target localization and tracking, addressing the shortcomings of traditional methods and demonstrating the potential of time series forecasting in wireless communication challenges. The TFT architecture is adapted to forecast the positions of multiple targets over various horizons, utilizing its advanced temporal modeling and dynamic feature selection capabilities. Simulation results underscore the effectiveness of TFT in enhancing target localization, providing a robust, interpretable, and scalable solution to critical issues in array signal processing. Comparative evaluations with state-of-the-art neural networks prove that TFT combines both accuracy and computational efficiency.

Index Terms—Direction of arrival (DoA) estimation, temporal fusion transformers (TFT), deep learning, time series forecasting

I. INTRODUCTION

In the framework of multiple-input multiple-output (MIMO) systems, beamforming techniques have become essential for directing transmission energy toward target directions, optimizing signal strength at the intended receiver, and minimizing interference in undesired directions. Beamforming not only enhances the performance of MIMO systems but also improves the energy efficiency and range of wireless communication systems. Central to beamforming applications is the direction of arrival (DoA) estimation. Beyond 5G (B5G) networks, characterized by ultra-dense deployments and the use of millimeter-wave (mmWave) frequencies, demand precise localization techniques to ensure reliable communication in highly dynamic environments. In this context, target localization plays a critical role in applications such as autonomous vehicles and UAVs, where real-time tracking of objects and users is essential for system functionality.

Kalman filters are fundamental in linear scenarios. Extensions like the extended and unscented Kalman filters enhance their ability to handle nonlinear systems [1]. However, they face challenges with complex, non-Gaussian noise and dynamic environments. Machine learning (ML) approaches,

especially deep learning, provide robust alternatives. Recurrent neural networks and long short-term memory (LSTM) networks excel in processing sequential data. Transformers [2], with their attention mechanisms, improve multi-horizon forecasting and real-time adaptability, making them suitable for advanced applications in B5G networks. Key advancements in wireless localization include [3], which enhances localization in challenging environments, [4], which employs intelligent surfaces to improve indoor localization for multiple users, and [5], which explores adaptive fusion techniques for harsh conditions. [6] presents an innovative method for long-term target tracking using correlation filters, significantly improving tracking performance in challenging scenarios with abrupt motion. [7] introduces a vision transformer-based approach for DoA estimation in low signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) environments, whereas [8] offers a comprehensive review of object detection techniques utilizing deep learning models in various object detection tasks. Moreover, [9] combines traditional tracking algorithms with machine learning for improved accuracy in dynamic settings, [10] presents an FFNN-based system for DoA estimation in 6G wireless communications, and [11] discusses active sensing schemes for beam-space MIMO radar in integrated sensing and communication applications. Research on forecasting techniques to enhance DoA estimation remains limited, underscoring a significant gap that our work seeks to address.

Temporal fusion transformers (TFTs) [12] represent a recent advancement in the field of time series forecasting, offering several unique features. Designed for multi-horizon time series forecasting, TFTs integrate both static and time-varying covariates, enabling them to model complex temporal patterns. As a transformer, the strength of the TFT architecture lies in its ability to capture both short and long-term dependencies in time series data, which is crucial for predicting the trajectory of moving targets. Unlike other ML and transformer models, which may rely on manual feature engineering, TFT employs dynamic feature selection through gating mechanisms, allowing the model to focus on the most relevant information at each time step. Moreover, the interpretability of TFTs is a distinguishing factor, as they provide insights into the underlying data relationships and model decisions, a key advantage for applications requiring transparency.

To the authors' best knowledge, no current work studies

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the implementation of the TFT model to target localization and tracking in the context of DoA estimation. Driven by this gap, in this work, we adapt the TFT architecture to the specific requirements of DoA estimation, including the preprocessing of sensor array data, the integration of relevant features, and the creation of a suitable dataset. We fine-tune the model and conduct extensive experiments to optimize the performance of TFT across various scenarios, including different forecast horizons, multiple target recognition and prediction times. We analyze the interpretability of TFT's predictions, offering insights into the model's decision-making process and highlighting the importance of features extracted from the targets' movement as captured by the sensors. Finally, we compare the results of TFT with state-of-the-art methods and recent ML-based approaches.

II. SYSTEM MODEL

A. Signal Description

In a three-dimensional space, incoming signals are specified by angle pairs (θ_n, ϕ_n) , where n ranges from 1 to N , N indicating the total number of incoming signals. Each signal is associated with a modulation function g_n . The spatial direction of each signal can be described using spherical coordinates with the direction vector \mathbf{v}_n :

$$\mathbf{v}_n = \cos \phi_n \sin \theta_n \mathbf{x}_0 + \sin \phi_n \cos \theta_n \mathbf{y}_0 + \cos \theta_n \mathbf{z}_0, \quad (1)$$

where \mathbf{x}_0 , \mathbf{y}_0 , and \mathbf{z}_0 are the unit vectors along the x, y, and z axes, respectively. The corresponding steering vector α_n can be expressed as:

$$\alpha_n = \begin{bmatrix} \exp(j2\pi f_c \tau_1(\theta_n, \phi_n)) \\ \exp(j2\pi f_c \tau_2(\theta_n, \phi_n)) \\ \vdots \\ \exp(j2\pi f_c \tau_M(\theta_n, \phi_n)) \end{bmatrix}, \quad (2)$$

where f_c is the carrier frequency and M is the number of antennas. The steering vector α_n for each signal is influenced by the time delay $\tau_m(\theta_n, \phi_n)$ of the signal reaching each antenna element. This time delay is given by:

$$\tau_m(\theta_n, \phi_n) = \frac{\mathbf{r}_m \cdot \mathbf{v}_n}{c}, \quad m = 1, \dots, M \quad (3)$$

where c is the speed of light and \mathbf{r}_m denotes the position vector of the m -th antenna element. The steering matrix \mathbf{A} , of size $M \times N$, consolidates all steering vectors:

$$\mathbf{A} = [\alpha_1 \quad \alpha_2 \quad \dots \quad \alpha_N]. \quad (4)$$

This matrix captures the spatial characteristics of the incoming signals. The time dependencies captured through τ_m are essential, as they allow the model to grasp and utilize the temporal dynamics inherent in the signal data. In addition, sensors continuously monitor the changing positions of a moving target, generating time-dependent data that reflect not only spatial coordinates but also the velocity and trajectory of the object over time. By incorporating these time delays and modulations, TFT can accurately model the complex time-varying patterns in the data, enhancing both predictive

accuracy and robustness. This capability addresses the limitations of traditional methods, which often struggle to capture temporal relationships in dynamic environments, thus enabling TFT to perform better in scenarios with rapidly changing conditions and signal variations.

B. Dataset

Our dataset simulates the dynamic movement of multiple targets over a 5,000-second period, with measurements for each target presented in parallel and concatenated. The targets' positions are represented in spherical coordinates, with their movement defined by two angles: θ (elevation) and ϕ (azimuth). A probabilistic model is incorporated into the simulation to introduce realistic movement changes, significantly influencing the prediction and tracking accuracy of various models. Movement updates occur every second and are subject to directional changes, with incremental shifts ranging from -1 to 1 degrees every 10 seconds. This frequency ensures the model can learn from regular, but not overly frequent, changes. These changes occur with a probability of 40%, adding an element of unpredictability that mimics real-world conditions, where movement trajectories are rarely linear or fully predictable. To ensure smoother real-world alike transitions in target movement, we introduced a damping factor, which reduces the speed when direction changes and makes the shifts in movement gradual. The dataset includes simulated signal strength based on the distance from the sensor, normalized between 0 (min) and 1 (max) with a defined maximum range. The dynamic nature of the dataset is further enhanced by incorporating historical data on position and velocity changes of the targets. This combination of signal strength variations and historical data updates provides a robust platform for analyzing and testing tracking algorithms under conditions of dynamic environments. In summary, dataset dimensions are equal to $(y \times 5000) \times 5$, where the five features are ϕ , θ , velocity of change of ϕ , velocity of change of θ , and signal strength, with y denoting the number of targets investigated.

To provide a comprehensive overview to the dataset, the following table presents descriptive statistics for each variable in the dataset, assuming 2 targets (10^4 samples).

TABLE I
DESCRIPTIVE STATISTICS FOR THE DATASET.

	θ ($^\circ$)	ϕ ($^\circ$)	$\theta_{vel.}$ ($\frac{^\circ}{s}$)	$\phi_{vel.}$ ($\frac{^\circ}{s}$)	Sig. Strength
mean	272.7	123.7	0.03	-0.1	0.563
std	111	71.066	0.563	0.559	0.367
min	30	0	-1	-1	0.263
25%	194.8	69.6	-0.4	-0.5	0.327
50%	235.45	130.8	0	0	0.557
75%	366.3	172.9	0.5	0.5	0.691
max	539	279	1	1	0.895

Fig. 1 illustrates the evolution of θ and ϕ over time for 2 moving targets, representing their dynamic movement in spherical coordinates. Both angles exhibit the targets' motion in three-dimensional space, showcasing the changing elevation (θ) and azimuth (ϕ) values. This time-series data forms the

basis for the TFT model to recognize underlying patterns and forecast future movements. It is important to note that both the θ and ϕ angles are post-processed to ensure they remain within specified ranges and can be accurately depicted in 3D space. θ is restricted within the interval $[0^\circ - 60^\circ]$, while ϕ is restricted within the interval $[0^\circ - 360^\circ]$. To achieve this, we apply $\theta \bmod 60$ for θ and $\phi \bmod 360$ for ϕ .

Fig. 1. Simulated target movement in 3D space.

III. MODEL ARCHITECTURE

A. TFT Mechanisms

The TFT architecture is based on several key features [12]. Gating mechanisms are essential as they adaptively manage the influence of different features and control the extent of non-linear processing. The gated residual network (GRN) integrates primary inputs with optional context vectors to determine the relevance and contribution of each feature dynamically. The GRN processes input \mathbf{a} and context \mathbf{c} :

$$\text{GRN}(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{c}) = \text{LayerNorm}(\mathbf{a} + \text{GLU}(\mathbf{h}_1)), \quad (5)$$

$$\mathbf{h}_1 = W_{1,\gamma} \mathbf{h}_2 + b_{1,\gamma}, \quad (6)$$

$$\mathbf{h}_2 = \text{ELU}(W_{2,\gamma} \mathbf{a} + W_{3,\gamma} \mathbf{c} + b_{2,\gamma}). \quad (7)$$

In these equations, $\text{LayerNorm}(\cdot)$ denotes layer normalization, $\text{ELU}(\cdot)$ is the exponential linear unit activation function, \mathbf{h}_1 and \mathbf{h}_2 are intermediate representations within the GRN and $W_{1,\gamma}$, $W_{2,\gamma}$, $W_{3,\gamma}$, $b_{1,\gamma}$, $b_{2,\gamma}$ are the weight matrices and biases, with γ indexing weight sharing across layers. Gated linear unit (GLU) is used to control the contribution of the GRN's output:

$$\text{GLU}(\mathbf{h}) = \sigma(W_{4,\gamma} \mathbf{h} + b_{4,\gamma}) \odot (W_{5,\gamma} \mathbf{h} + b_{5,\gamma}), \quad (8)$$

where $\sigma(\cdot)$ represents the sigmoid activation function, which produces gating values between 0 and 1 and \odot denotes the element-wise Hadamard product. Dropout is applied before the gating layer and layer normalization to enhance model robustness and prevent overfitting.

Variable selection networks enhance model performance by identifying relevant features and reducing the impact of noisy inputs. Categorical variables use entity embeddings, while continuous ones undergo linear transformations into a d_{model} -dimensional vector. Separate variable selection networks process static, past, and future inputs, though their structure remains consistent across these types. For past inputs, the transformed input vectors $\mathbf{x}_t^{(j)} \in \mathbb{R}^{d_{\text{model}}}$ are aggregated into a flattened vector \mathbf{x}_t . Variable selection weights $\mathbf{v}_t \in \mathbb{R}^m$ are then computed by applying a GRN to \mathbf{x}_t and an external context vector \mathbf{c}_s , followed by a softmax activation:

$$\mathbf{v}_t = \text{Softmax}(\text{GRN}_v(\mathbf{x}_t, \mathbf{c}_s)) \quad (9)$$

Here, GRN_v denotes the GRN used for generating variable selection weights, and Softmax normalizes these weights. For static variables, the context vector \mathbf{c}_s is omitted since static information is inherently available. Moreover, each variable $\mathbf{x}_t^{(j)}$ is processed through its own GRN to capture non-linear relationships:

$$\tilde{\mathbf{x}}_t^{(j)} = \text{GRN}_{\tilde{\mathbf{x}}}^{(j)}(\mathbf{x}_t^{(j)}), \quad (10)$$

where $\tilde{\mathbf{x}}_t^{(j)}$ represents the processed feature vector for the j -th variable. The final feature representation at each time step is computed by weighting and combining these processed features:

$$\tilde{\mathbf{x}}_t = \sum_{j=1}^m v_t^{(j)} \tilde{\mathbf{x}}_t^{(j)}, \quad (11)$$

where $v_t^{(j)}$ is the j -th element of the variable selection weight vector \mathbf{v}_t . This process ensures that only the most relevant features contribute to the model's predictions.

Static covariates are incorporated into TFT architecture through the use of dedicated GRN encoders. These encoders produce four distinct context vectors: \mathbf{c}_s , \mathbf{c}_e , \mathbf{c}_c , and \mathbf{c}_h , each serving specific roles in the model's processing pipeline. Context vector \mathbf{c}_s helps select relevant temporal features, while \mathbf{c}_c and \mathbf{c}_h facilitate local processing of temporal patterns. Context vector \mathbf{c}_e integrates static covariates into temporal features, providing a richer understanding of the data. These vectors are also used in the temporal fusion decoder, ensuring static information is effectively utilized.

Moreover, TFT incorporates a self-attention mechanism to capture long-term dependencies across different time steps, enhancing the model's interpretability compared to traditional multi-head attention used in transformer architectures. In a typical attention mechanism, the attention function scales values $\mathbf{V} \in \mathbb{R}^{N \times d_v}$ based on relationships between keys $\mathbf{K} \in \mathbb{R}^{N \times d_{\text{attn}}}$ and queries $\mathbf{Q} \in \mathbb{R}^{N \times d_{\text{attn}}}$ as follows:

$$\text{Attention}(\mathbf{Q}, \mathbf{K}, \mathbf{V}) = A(\mathbf{Q}, \mathbf{K}) \mathbf{V}, \quad (12)$$

where $A()$ represents a normalization function. The scaled dot-product attention is a common choice for $A()$:

$$A(\mathbf{Q}, \mathbf{K}) = \text{Softmax}\left(\frac{\mathbf{Q}\mathbf{K}^T}{\sqrt{d_{\text{attn}}}}\right). \quad (13)$$

To enhance the model's learning capacity, multi-head attention is employed. This approach uses multiple heads to capture different representation subspaces:

$$\text{MultiHead}(\mathbf{Q}, \mathbf{K}, \mathbf{V}) = [\mathbf{H}_1; \dots; \mathbf{H}_{m_H}] \mathbf{W}_H, \quad (14)$$

where each head \mathbf{H}_h is computed as:

$$\mathbf{H}_h = \text{Attention}(\mathbf{Q} \mathbf{W}_Q^{(h)}, \mathbf{K} \mathbf{W}_K^{(h)}, \mathbf{V} \mathbf{W}_V^{(h)}), \quad (15)$$

with $\mathbf{W}_K^{(h)}$, $\mathbf{W}_Q^{(h)}$, and $\mathbf{W}_V^{(h)}$ being head-specific weights for keys, queries, and values, respectively. The final output is obtained by linearly combining the outputs from all heads:

$$\text{MultiHead}(\mathbf{Q}, \mathbf{K}, \mathbf{V}) = [\mathbf{H}_1; \dots; \mathbf{H}_{m_H}] \mathbf{W}_H. \quad (16)$$

In TFT this approach is modified to improve interpretability by sharing values across all heads and aggregating the outputs additively:

$$\text{InterpretableMultiHead}(\mathbf{Q}, \mathbf{K}, \mathbf{V}) = \tilde{\mathbf{H}} \mathbf{W}_H, \quad (17)$$

where

$$\tilde{\mathbf{H}} = \frac{1}{H} \sum_{h=1}^{m_H} \tilde{A}(\mathbf{Q} \mathbf{W}_Q^{(h)}, \mathbf{K} \mathbf{W}_K^{(h)}) \mathbf{V} \mathbf{W}_V. \quad (18)$$

Here, \mathbf{W}_V are value weights shared across all heads, and \mathbf{W}_H is used for the final linear mapping. This modification ensures that each head learns different temporal patterns while attending to a common set of input features, providing an ensemble-like effect over attention weights and improving representational efficiency.

TFT's temporal fusion decoder models time series relationships using a sequence-to-sequence architecture. It processes historical and future inputs to generate uniform temporal features and generates $\tilde{\mathbf{e}}(t, n)$:

$$\tilde{\mathbf{e}}(t, n) = \text{LayerNorm}(\tilde{\mathbf{x}}_{t+n} + \text{GLU}_{\tilde{\mathbf{e}}}(\mathbf{e}(t, n))), \quad (19)$$

where $\text{GLU}_{\tilde{\mathbf{e}}}$ is a gated linear unit. Static metadata is incorporated to enrich temporal features using a static enrichment layer. The enriched features are computed as:

$$\mathbf{s}(t, n) = \text{GRN}_{\mathbf{s}}(\tilde{\mathbf{e}}(t, n), \mathbf{c}_e), \quad (20)$$

where \mathbf{c}_e is the static context vector. Self-attention is applied to enriched temporal features to capture long-range dependencies. The attention mechanism is defined as:

$$B(t) = \text{InterpretableMultiHead}(\mathbf{S}(t), \mathbf{S}(t), \mathbf{S}(t)). \quad (21)$$

The output of the self-attention layer undergoes additional non-linear processing through a position-wise feed-forward layer:

$$\tilde{\mathbf{s}}(t, n) = \text{LayerNorm}(\tilde{\mathbf{e}}(t, n) + \text{GLU}_{\tilde{\mathbf{s}}}(\mathbf{s}(t, n))). \quad (22)$$

Fig. 2. TFT architecture.

B. Hyperparameter Tuning and Proposed Architecture

Aiming to tune the model's hyperparameters, we test various configurations for the forecasting task. In our analysis, hidden layer sizes range from 8 to 64 to balance learning capacity with overfitting risk. Hidden continuous size, which control the number of units in continuous representation layers, also vary between 8 and 64. Attention head size influences the number of attention mechanisms, helping to capture temporal relationships and in our analysis vary from 1 to 4. The learning rate ranged between 0.001 to 0.1, while dropout rates, used to prevent overfitting without underfitting, vary from 0.1 to 0.3. The final hyperparameters for the TFT model, determined through this comprehensive tuning process, are as follows: a learning rate of 0.001, a hidden layer size of 32, hidden continuous size of 16, an attention head size of 2 and a dropout rate of 0.1. These settings represent a balanced trade-off between model complexity, training efficiency, and generalization performance, ensuring that the TFT architecture is well-suited for the forecasting task at hand.

The proposed TFT model architecture consists of 76.8K trainable parameters. Key components include multi-embedding and variable selection network modules, with separate networks for static, encoder, and decoder variables, containing 5.8K, 9.8K, and 7.8K parameters, respectively. GRN layers handle context enrichment and initialization of the LSTM's hidden and cell states, each with 4.3K parameters, enhancing the model's ability to capture temporal dependencies. The LSTM encoder and decoder, each with 8.4K parameters, perform core sequential learning tasks. An interpretable multi-head attention mechanism, with 3.2K parameters, captures long-term dependencies. Finally, GLU and normalization modules control information flow and mitigate overfitting, resulting in a total of 76.8K parameters.

IV. SIMULATION RESULTS

In our analysis we measure the angular error through multiple metrics, including mean absolute error (MAE) which in our analysis is given as:

$$\text{MAE} = \frac{1}{k} \sum_{i=1}^k \left(\left| \hat{\theta}_i - \theta_i \right| + \left| \hat{\phi}_i - \phi_i \right| \right), \quad (23)$$

root mean square error (RMSE):

$$\text{RMSE} = \sqrt{\frac{1}{k} \left(\sum_{i=1}^k (\hat{\theta}_i - \theta_i)^2 + \sum_{i=1}^n (\hat{\phi}_i - \phi_i)^2 \right)}, \quad (24)$$

and symmetric mean absolute percentage error (SMAPE), which is a percentage-based error metric that scales the absolute error by the average of the predicted and actual angles:

$$\text{SMAPE} = \frac{1}{k} \sum_{i=1}^k \left(\frac{|\hat{\theta}_i - \theta_i|}{\frac{1}{2} (|\hat{\theta}_i| + |\theta_i|)} + \frac{|\hat{\phi}_i - \phi_i|}{\frac{1}{2} (|\hat{\phi}_i| + |\phi_i|)} \right) \%. \quad (25)$$

In these equations, k represents the total number of target movement samples, θ and ϕ represent the actual angles, whereas $\hat{\theta}$ and $\hat{\phi}$ represent the predicted angles.

Fig. 3. Tracking validation for 1 target.

Fig. 3 illustrates the relationship between the actual and predicted values of the angular variables θ and ϕ during the model's validation process for 600 timesteps. The dashed red line represents the predicted angle values generated by the TFT model, while the actual values are depicted by the solid blue line. The predicted values closely align with the distribution of the actual data, demonstrating the model's effectiveness in capturing the angular movement patterns over time. The model successfully identifies the peaks and directional shifts.

TABLE II
PRECISION ANALYSIS FOR MULTIPLE SIMULTANEOUS TARGETS.

Number of Targets	MAE (°)	RMSE (°)	SMAPE (%)
1	0.045	0.07	0.07
2	0.065	0.1	0.11
3	0.15	0.24	0.14
4	0.22	0.36	0.16
5	0.27	0.47	0.19

Table II showcases promising performance for precision analysis across multiple simultaneous targets. MAE increases slightly from 0.045° for a single target to 0.27° with five

targets, while the RMSE grows from 0.07° to 0.47° , and SMAPE rises from 0.07% to 0.19% . Despite these increases, the error values remain impressively low, demonstrating high precision even as the number of targets increases.

When comparing our proposed TFT with state-of-the-art neural networks, including an LSTM, a transformer and a dynamic linear model (DLM), several key distinctions emerge. In our comparative analysis, we include an LSTM model with 128 hidden units, 5 input features utilizing a single-layer LSTM for sequential data processing followed by a linear regression layer. We also incorporate a transformer model with 64 hidden units, 4 attention heads and 2 hidden layers. For the DLM, the architecture includes a second-degree trend component, an autoregressive component of degree equal to 2 for temporal dependencies, and a seasonal component to address periodic fluctuations.

Fig. 4. Comparison analysis for 2 targets and multi-horizon predictions.

As shown in Fig. 4, where 2 targets are considered, at a prediction horizon of 1, the proposed model achieves its best performance, with a RMSE of 0.087° . As the prediction horizon increases, the error metrics rise slightly, but remain remarkably low. The RMSE stays below 0.5° for up to 20 horizons and below 1° for up to 38 horizons. These results demonstrate that the model's accuracy remains impressively stable across a wide range of horizons, providing robust performance even at extended time forecasts. The performance of the DLM and the transformer begin to decline significantly after 3 horizons, as they lack the architecture depth and attention layers included in our proposed model. Moreover, the proposed TFT outperforms the LSTM model, achieving nearly three times better accuracy. The LSTM outperforming the transformer model can be attributed to the specific structure and characteristics of the dataset.

Table III presents the prediction times for the two most accurate models from our previous analysis across various prediction horizons. As shown, the TFT consistently outperforms the LSTM in terms of speed. At a prediction horizon of 1, the TFT completes predictions in 0.123 milliseconds, significantly

faster than the LSTM’s 0.456 ms. This difference increases with longer horizons, becoming 4 times faster at a horizon of 50.

TABLE III
COMPARISON OF TIME REQUIRED FOR PREDICTIONS FOR VARIOUS PREDICTION HORIZONS.

Prediction Horizons	TFT (ms)	LSTM (ms)
1	0.123	0.456
10	1.456	3.234
25	3.789	9.345
50	4.234	16.567

In Fig. 5, the overall prediction performance of the TFT model is evaluated, focusing on its ability to distinguish multiple simultaneous received signals from different targets. The evaluation is based on 1000 random ϕ angles, with the frequency of each respective target shown on the right y-axis. The plot compares the predicted and actual angles for five targets, with the average azimuth position of each target depicted. The results demonstrate the model’s accuracy in tracking multiple distinct targets with varying movement patterns. The TFT model accurately follows their independent trajectories, and reliably forecasts their behavior over time.

Fig. 5. Multiple target recognition validation.

TABLE IV
ENCODER VARIABLES IMPORTANCE.

Encoder Variable	Importance (%)
Monitored Past Angles	60
Signal Strength	25
Monitored Past Angle Velocity	15

Table IV provides a detailed analysis of feature importance within the encoder components of the TFT model. The bar plot reveals that the monitored angles and the calculated signal strength are the two most significant features utilized by the encoder, underscoring the importance of spatial positioning and time-based characteristics. While angular velocity also

contributes, its influence is comparatively smaller. The interpretable results aid in optimizing and understanding the model’s decision-making process, highlighting areas where improvements to the input data could enhance the model’s training and prediction accuracy.

V. CONCLUSIONS

This work explores the implementation of the TFT model for multi-horizon target localization forecasting, emphasizing its ability to accurately predict 3D positioning over extended time horizons, essential for tracking moving targets. The model demonstrates impressive performance, achieving less than 0.5° of error for up to 5 simultaneous targets with a 1-horizon forecast and under 1° of error for 2 targets for up to 50 horizons. It effectively captures nonlinear data relationships, distinguishes multiple targets, forecasts average movement patterns, and dynamically prioritizes input variables, showcasing flexible feature selection through encoder mechanisms. Future research should enhance the model’s adaptability to more complex scenarios, further improve multi-horizon accuracy, and explore integration with other DoA estimation techniques to advance array signal processing and develop comprehensive real-world applications.

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